

Sociodemographic And Psychological Factors as Determinants of Academic Resilience Among Undergraduates in Southwestern Nigeria Universities

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ABSTRACT

Academic resilience, the ability to persevere and succeed despite educational challenges, plays a critical role in student retention and performance, particularly in resource-constrained higher education systems like Nigeria's. Undergraduates in South-West Nigeria face numerous stressors, including institutional disruptions, socioeconomic pressures, and personal adjustments, making resilience a vital psychological resource. This study examined the predictive roles of body image, locus of control, and parenting style on academic resilience, while also exploring differences across gender, marital status, university type, and level of study.

239 undergraduates purposively sampled from private, federal, and state universities in South-West Nigeria. Participants completed standardized self-report measures assessing academic resilience, body image satisfaction, locus of control orientation, and perceived parenting style. Data were analyzed using Pearson correlation, multiple linear regression, independent samples t-tests, and one-way ANOVA (including Welch's variant for robustness). Assumptions of normality, homogeneity, and linearity were verified prior to inferential analyses.

Results revealed that the correlation matrix showed that academic resilience significantly correlated positively with body image ($r = 0.406$, $p < .001$) and locus of control ($r = 0.213$, $p < .001$), but not with parenting style ($r = 0.093$, ns). Body image and locus of control were also strongly correlated ($r = 0.365$, $p < .001$), whereas parenting style demonstrated weak negative relationships with both body image ($r = -0.166$, $p < .05$) and locus of control ($r = -0.097$, ns). The regression model predicting academic resilience was significant ($F(3,235) = 19.20$, $p < .001$), accounting for 19.7% of variance ($R^2 = .197$). Body image was the dominant predictor ($\beta = .404$, $p < .001$), followed by a modest significant effect of parenting style ($\beta = .168$, $p = .005$), while locus of control became non-significant ($\beta = .082$, $p = .195$).

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Gender-based comparison showed no significant difference in academic resilience, $t(237) = -0.169$, $p = .866$, with a negligible effect size ($d \approx .02$). Marital status also showed no significant effect, $t(237) = -1.68$, $p = .094$, though married students displayed slightly higher resilience ($d \approx .44$). In contrast, academic resilience differed significantly by university type, $F(2,236) = 8.18$, $p < .001$, with private university students scoring highest. Significant differences were also observed across levels of study, Welch's $F(4,96.4) = 3.74$, $p = .007$, with resilience increasing progressively and peaking among 500-level students.

These findings emphasize the central role of positive body image in fostering academic resilience among Nigerian undergraduates, while suggesting limited direct influence of locus of control and parenting style. Institutional context and academic progression further shape resilience outcomes. It is recommended that universities integrate body-positive counseling initiatives, provide resilience-building programs especially for lower-level students, and improve supportive resources within public institutions to strengthen students' adaptive functioning and academic success.

Keywords: Age, Gender, Locus of Control, Body Image, Academic Resilience, Gender, Parenting Style, Locus of Control, Body Image, Academic Resilience

INTRODUCTION

Academic Resilience is a critical component of students' achievement and success. It encompasses cognitive, affective and behavioral response to difficulties or challenges students are faced with in their academic pursuit, involving self efficacy, sense of control, persistent and composure. In recent years, the well-being of university students has become a major global concern. Research consistently shows that undergraduates face high levels of stress, anxiety, and emotional challenges that interfere with their studies. This is true not only in developed countries but also in developing countries. The outbreak of COVID-19 further intensified these pressures, disrupting academic calendars, increasing uncertainty, and creating new psychological burdens.

A recent meta-analysis covering African universities estimated that more than 64% of students experience significant stress, which points to a worrying trend across the continent (Fentahun, Haile, and Belachew, 2025). The frequent rates of perseverance, struggles and adjustment that students in the University are forced to face and make are due to different psychological, social, economic and environmental challenges the students are exposed to and which stands as hindrances to their academic achievement this can be linked with academic resilience. Academic resilience helps the students to look beyond their challenges whether from (the family and society) and cope with life and still be very successful academically.

Global health agencies such as the World Health Organization also confirm that late adolescence and early adulthood (18-25 years) the age group that makes up most undergraduates has become a period when mental health disorders such as depression and anxiety are especially common (World Health Organization, 2025). This happens because it is believed that at this stage the child is aware of what is happening around him, so there is the feeling of responsibility that comes on the children in the stage and this can also affect their academic achievement if enough resilience has not been built.

In Sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria in particular, academic resilience takes on added importance. The higher education (such as: University education) system is under constant pressure due to overcrowded classrooms, inadequate facilities, and frequent strikes that disrupt academic calendars. Scholars often describe this as the massification of higher education i.e. rapid enrollment growth without a proportional expansion of resources (Altbach, Reisberg, and Rumbley, 2019; Tadesse and Melese, 2023). These conditions produce a stressful learning environment where only students who can adapt and remain focused are likely to succeed.

Research also shows that for students to pursue and attain academic success their resilience i.e. ability to stand and be successful despite all odds should be encouraged, because of this, researchers and educators have turned their attention to the concept of academic resilience. Academic resilience is the ability of students to recover, adapt, and succeed despite academic setbacks, stress, or disadvantage.

Rather than seeing resilience as a fixed personality trait, scholars now describe it as a dynamic process that can be strengthened by both internal and external factors. For example, personal attitudes like self-efficacy and optimism, as well as external supports like parental involvement or teacher encouragement, all contribute to resilience. Students with higher resilience generally achieve better academic results and show lower levels of stress, anxiety, and depression.

Recent studies in higher education show that resilience mediates the link between support (e.g., from teachers or peers) and performance outcomes (Abdelrahman, 2025; Cai, Li, and Zhang, 2025). In other words, these authors believe that students thrive more academically when the external locus of control are put in place.

Academic resilience refers to a student's capacity to effectively navigate, adapt to, and recover from academic challenges, setbacks, and adverse circumstances while maintaining progress toward educational goals. In the university context where course rigor, social transitions, financial pressure, and institutional expectations converge resilience functions as a protective factor that enables students to persist and succeed despite risk exposures. In sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria in particular, persistent constraints such as under funding of higher education, large class sizes, infrastructural deficits, and socioeconomic disparities can heighten vulnerability to academic stress. Within these settings, identifying modifiable determinants of resilience is both theoretically important and practically urgent for student support services (Ungar, 2019).

Tudor and Spray, 2017 says that, Academic resilience is often based on two core components: risk or adverse circumstances affecting student progress, and positive adaptation, which involves overcoming these challenges and thriving academically. Such risk factors frequently encompass demographic characteristics (e.g., ethnic identity), available resources (e.g., socio-economic status of the family), interpersonal relationships (e.g., those with peers), health-related and academic hurdles (e.g., school-based discrimination). Martin and Marsh (2006) identified five key motivational predictors of academic buoyancy, known as the 5-Cs: Confidence, Coordination, Control, Composure, and Commitment. These components describe the personal attributes that help students successfully navigate, adapt to, and overcome the everyday setbacks and challenges of academic life, rather than focusing on significant, chronic adversity.

Nigerian studies confirm that undergraduate students report very high stress levels, including burnout and loss of motivation (Ogunsola, 2023). This makes it essential to identify what socio-demographic and psychological factors contribute to resilience in Nigerian universities. Socio-demographic factors such as gender, age, and parenting style play a strong role in shaping resilience. Gender differences in resilience and academic stress have been widely studied, though the results vary across contexts. Some studies show female students report higher academic stress than males, while other research finds males may disengage more when stressed (Chukwu and Okafor, 2022). Age also matters: younger students may still be adjusting to the university environment, whereas older students often draw on greater maturity or experience to manage difficulties.

Parenting style is another key influence which is rooted in Baumrind's parenting style theory of authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful styles shapes the development of autonomy, self efficacy, and coping strategies from adolescence into emerging adulthood (Moghaddam et al., 2017). Research based on Social Cognitive Theory also shows that supportive and balanced parenting (authoritative style) predicts higher self-efficacy and motivation, which in turn foster resilience (Shengyao, Xiaohui, and Lijuan, 2024). In contrast, very strict or neglectful parenting is associated with poor emotional coping and lower academic adjustment. Nigerian studies confirm that parental support and involvement influence students' motivation, adjustment, and burnout risk, all of which relate closely to resilience (Olufemi & Adepoju, 2022; Oyetunde, 2023).

On the psychological side, two factors are particularly relevant for Nigerian undergraduates (for this study): body image and locus of control. Body image refers to how individuals perceive and feel about their physical appearance. Poor body image has become a growing concern worldwide, especially among young people who are influenced by social media and cultural expectations of attractiveness. Negative body image is strongly linked to low self-esteem, depression, and reduced academic engagement. In Nigeria, several studies reveal that many young people are dissatisfied with their body image. For instance, a study in Benin City found a high prevalence of body image dissatisfaction among adolescents (Olatona et al., 2023), and

more recent work in Nigerian universities has linked poor body image with depression and reduced academic functioning (Akinyemi et al., 2025). A positive body image can also facilitate social integration, self confidence, and stress management, while body dissatisfaction may be linked to anxiety, depressive symptoms, and avoidance behaviors that compromise academic persistence (Voelker et al., 2015). This suggests that body image challenges may undermine resilience in undergraduates.

Locus of control (LOC) is another psychological determinant closely tied to resilience. Locus of control refers to the degree to which people believe outcomes in their lives are controlled by their own actions (internal Locus of control) or by external factors such as luck, fate, or other people (external locus of control). Students with a strong internal locus of control tend to believe their academic success depends on their effort, and this belief motivates them to work harder and to persevere through challenges. Conversely, students with an external locus of control attributes success to luck, fate, chances etc and this may make them feel powerless, leading them to give up more easily when faced with difficulties. Research in African contexts, including Ghana and Nigeria, shows that internal Locus of control is strongly associated with better academic performance and greater resilience (Aidoo et al., 2024; Adekeye and Fasakin, 2022). Locus of control whether individuals attribute outcomes to internal factors (effort, strategy, ability) or external forces (luck, fate, powerful others) influences motivation, persistence, and responses to feedback (Zhang et al., 2022).

Bringing these ideas together, it is clear that resilience among undergraduates is influenced by both socio-demographic factors (gender, age, parenting style) and psychological factors (body image and locus of control).

However, most studies in Nigeria have looked at these variables separately rather than combining them into one model. This leaves an important gap in understanding, since in reality, resilience is shaped by a mixture of social background and psychological traits. Very few studies have explored this integrated approach within Southwestern Nigeria universities, even though these institutions face unique pressures linked to urbanization, diverse student populations, and infrastructural challenges.

Therefore, the present study seeks to investigate how socio-demographic factors (gender, age, parenting style) and psychological factors (body image, locus of control) jointly determine academic resilience among undergraduates in Southwestern Nigeria. By examining these variables together, the study will provide a richer and more accurate understanding of resilience in this context. The findings are expected to guide practical interventions such as parental guidance programs, resilience-building workshops, counseling services, and body image awareness campaigns. These measures will not only improve academic success but also enhance the overall wellbeing of undergraduates in Nigeria.

Southwestern Nigeria, hosts a dense cluster of public and private universities across Lagos, Oyo, Ogun, Osun, Ondo, and Ekiti States. The sub-region is culturally diverse and economically

dynamic, with substantial rural–urban contrasts and marked socioeconomic gradients. The student body is similarly diverse in age profiles (traditional and non-traditional students), gender composition, and family backgrounds. These contextual conditions provide a strategic setting to interrogate how gender, age, parenting style, body image, and locus of control jointly and differentially predict academic resilience among university undergraduates.

Statement of the Problem

Across the world, research has shown that university students are increasingly vulnerable to stress, anxiety, and depression. In Africa, this problem is even more pressing, as studies have reported that more than six out of every ten undergraduates experience significant stress during their academic journey.

In Nigeria, the situation is particularly challenging because of the combined effects of academic workload, unstable calendars due to strikes, limited learning facilities, and financial strain on students and their families. These pressures often lead to poor academic performance, withdrawal from school, or long-term emotional difficulties. While many universities have recognized this crisis, only a few have developed targeted strategies to build resilience in students.

The concept of academic resilience is the ability to persist and succeed in spite of challenges has been recognized as a protective factor against these risks. However, research in Nigeria has often focused narrowly on either demographic differences or psychological variables in isolation, rather than studying how they interact together to shape resilience. For example, while studies have examined gender and age differences in stress responses and others have explored parenting styles in relation to adjustment and burnout, very few have connected these social demographic factors such as (gender, age and parenting style) with psychological factors such as body image and locus of control.

Also, despite numerous institutional interventions, counselling centers, mentorship programs, tutoring scheme, academic underperformance remain notable concerns in universities across Southwestern Nigeria. Many students report difficulties recovering from poor grades, balancing work study responsibilities, coping with financial stress, or managing psychosocial pressures such as appearance-related concerns and adjustment to campus life. While isolated studies have examined single predictors of academic success, fewer have simultaneously modeled socio-demographic (gender, age, parenting style) and psychological (body image, locus of control) correlates in a unified framework of academic resilience.

This leaves a gap in understanding because resilience is rarely determined by a single factor. Instead, it is shaped by the interaction between socio-demographic realities (such as gender, age, and parenting) and psychological resources (such as body image satisfaction and locus of control). For instance, students raised in supportive homes may develop stronger self-confidence,

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but this resilience could still be undermined if they struggle with negative body image or an external locus of control. Conversely, a student who perceives strong personal control over outcomes (internal locus of control) may still face setbacks if coupled with poor parental support or age-related immaturity. Without examining these combined effects, universities cannot fully understand why some undergraduates cope effectively while others falter.

Another problem is the lack of context specific research in Southwestern Nigeria. Although international literature has documented resilience factors across Europe, Asia, and parts of Africa only a handful of studies focus specifically on Nigerian undergraduates. Even fewer focus on the Southwestern region, where universities host some of the largest student populations in the country. This neglect is troubling because the Southwestern context comes with unique pressures, including intense competition for limited resources, high urbanization, and diverse socio-cultural backgrounds. Findings from other regions cannot simply be generalized without careful local investigation.

Moreover, institutional policies often adopt one-size-fits-all approaches that may overlook subgroup differences. For example, younger entrants may require distinct scaffolds compared to older, returning students; students raised under authoritarian parenting may need autonomy-supportive coaching; and those with externalized control beliefs may benefit from attributional retraining. Without empirically identifying which factors most strongly influence resilience and for whom interventions risk being diffuse or misaligned.

Therefore, the present study seeks to investigate how socio-demographic factors (gender, age, parenting style) and psychological factors (body image, locus of control) jointly determine academic resilience among undergraduates in Southwestern Nigeria. By examining these variables together, the study will provide a richer and more accurate understanding of resilience in this context. The findings are expected to guide practical interventions such as parental guidance programs, resilience-building workshops, counseling services, and body image awareness campaigns. These measures will not only improve academic success but also enhance the overall wellbeing of undergraduates in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the "socio demographic and psychological factors as factors that determines academic resilience among undergraduates in southwestern universities in Nigeria. Specifically, this study investigates both the joint contribution and individual contribution of each of the independent variables (gender, age, parenting style, body image and locus of control) on the prediction of academic resilience among undergraduates in southwestern universities in Nigeria.

In specific terms, the sole objectives of this study include the following;

- i. Determine the relationship that exists among of all the independent variables (parenting style, locus of control and body image) and the dependent variable (academic resilience) of students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities

- ii. Investigate the joint contribution of all the independent variables (gender, age, parenting style, locus of control and body image) to the academic resilience of students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities
- iii. Explore the relative contribution of all the independent variables (parenting style, locus of control and body image) to the academic resilience of students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities
- iv. Examine gender differences in academic resilience among undergraduate students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities
- v. Determine differences in resilience based on the type of institution (whether private or public institution in Southwestern Nigeria Universities)
- vi. Determine differences in resilience based on level of study of students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship that exists among of all the independent variables (parenting style, locus of control and body image) and the dependent variable (academic resilience) of students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities?
2. What is the joint contribution of all the independent variables (gender, age, parenting style, locus of control and body image) to the academic resilience of students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities?
3. What is the relative contribution of all the independent variables (parenting style, locus of control and body image) to the academic resilience of students in Southwestern Nigeria Universities?

METHODOLOGY

Design

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design because it enables the researcher to collect factual information objectively and examine relationships among variables without manipulation (Creswell & Creswell, 2021; Schutt, 2021). This design is appropriate for assessing socio-demographic and psychological predictors of academic resilience among undergraduate students.

This study also adopts a correlational survey design within a post-positivist quantitative framework. Correlational design is selected because the aim of the study is to analyze the predictive and associative influences of socio-demographic variables (gender, age, and parenting style) and psychological determinants (body image and locus of control) on academic resilience.

Population

The study population comprises undergraduate students enrolled in accredited universities within Southwestern Nigeria. Specifically, the sampling frame will consist of six (6) selected universities across three states: Oyo, Lagos, and Osun. Two (2) universities were selected from each of the states to ensure proportional representation across federal, state, and private institutions (NUC, 2023).

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According to the NUC Nigerian University System Statistical Digest (2019), the number of undergraduates in Southwestern Nigeria Universities are (379,117) with total of (312,430) in public universities, which comprises of both federal and state universities and 66,687 undergraduates in private universities. According to this, there are about 82% of undergraduates' students in public universities and 18% in private universities.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique will be used. First, universities will be stratified based on ownership structure (federal, state, and private). Second, random selection will be used to choose two institutions from each state. Finally, proportionate sampling will be applied to determine the number of participants recruited from each selected university based on estimated student enrolment statistics.

Stage 1: Stratification by University Ownership: Federal, State and Private Universities

Stage 2: Random Selection of Universities: 2 from each stratum; (6 universities)

Stage 3: Proportionate Allocation: Sample proportional to each institution's enrolment prevents sampling dominance by large schools.

Stage 4: Simple Random Sampling of Students from 200–400 level, excluding first-year students due to transitional instability affecting resilience measures

Instrumentation

The study implores questionnaires for the data collection. The information retrieved for the study includes the demographic variables, Academic Resilience, Parenting Style, Locus of control and body image.

Section A: Demographic Information (e.g; age, gender, marital status, religion, education, level of study, and university type).

Section B: Academic Resilience Scale (10 items adapted from Cassidy, 2016).

Section C: Parenting Style Inventory (10 items adapted from Buri,1991).

Section D: Locus of Control Scale (10 items adapted from Rotter,1966).

Section E: Body Image Scale (adapted from Tylka and Wood-Barcalow 2015).

Section F: Open Ended Questions (have 3 questions)

Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

Demographic Characteristics

This section gathered basic background information from respondents. It consisted of 6 items designed to profile participants in terms of key socio-demographic factors relevant to the study of academic resilience. The variables covered include:

Gender: (Male/Female), Age groups: (below 18, 18-20, 21-23, 24-26, Above 26), Marital status: (e.g: Single/ Married), Religion: (e.g., Christianity, Islam, Others), University Type: (Federal, State or Private), Level of Study: (100, 200, 300 and above)

This section provided the baseline data necessary to explore demographic variations in academic resilience outcomes.

Academic Resilience Scale

This section assessed the dependent variable of the study “Academic Resilience” which refers to the capacity of undergraduate’s students to achieve positive academic outcomes despite the presence of adversities, stress, or disadvantages. It is characterized by the ability to cope with academic pressure, overcome challenges, and maintain motivation and high performance in the face of difficult circumstances, such as socioeconomic status, personal hardships, or learning difficulties. This scale was adapted from the Cassidy,2016 and further enriched with indicators from more recent instruments. It consisted of 10 items measuring the following dimensions: self efficacy, learning style, level of determination and concentration of the students. Sample items include: I can adapt my learning style when courses are difficult, I feel confident managing difficult academic tasks, I do not let discouragement stop me from trying again etc. Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Higher aggregate scores indicate higher levels of academic resilience

Parenting Style Inventory

This section measured the relationship between the students and their parents, it also what type of parenting style is been adopted by their parents (whether the authoritarian, authoritative, neglectful parenting style etc) The scale was adapted Buri 1991 parenting style inventory and consisted of 10 items. Sample items include: my parents encourage me to express my opinion freely, my parents believe children should be seen not heard, my parents hardly enforce any strict rules at home etc.

Locus of Control Scale

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This section evaluated respondents' motivation (whether intrinsic or extrinsic motivation), it also measures how they view success and failure and how they handle and manage setbacks. The scale, adapted from Rotter 1966, comprised 10 items. Sample items: “Internal factors mostly determine my academic outcomes”, “failure in school is often just a matter of bad luck”, “I am confident that I can influence my future” etc.

Body Image Scale

This section captures how respondents view or perceive themselves, how satisfy they are with their body structure and how confident they are. It is adapted from Tylka and Wood-Barcalow 2015. The scale consisted of 10 items. Sample items are: “I appreciate my body most of the time”, “I feel my appearance does not define my worth”, “I have positive attitude towards my body”. It is also measure by the 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly disagree to Strongly Agree

Open Ended Questions

This section is designed to know the personal view of the respondents on academic resilience and also how they navigate everything that comes with their studies.

Sample items: “what academic challenges do you face most frequently?”, “what helps you stay motivated when school becomes difficulty?”

Method of Data Collection

Data will be collected through an online survey using a structured digital questionnaire designed on Google Forms. After obtaining ethical approval and permission from the selected universities, the researcher will contact faculty representatives, departmental associations, and student leaders to facilitate the distribution of survey links via institutional email groups, Telegram and WhatsApp class platforms.

The online survey approach ensures wider accessibility and efficient coverage of all selected institutions, especially considering students' high engagement with mobile and digital communication tools. Participation instructions will be clearly stated at the beginning of the form. The survey will remain open for four weeks, with regular follow-up reminders sent to encourage maximum participation.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected will be coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, and standard deviation will be used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the respondents. To answer the research questions and test the hypotheses, inferential statistics will be used.

A Pearson Product Moment Correlation will be employed to examine the relationship between the psychological factors (body image and locus of control) and academic resilience. An Independent Samples t-test will be used to determine whether gender has a significant influence on academic resilience. Additionally, Multiple Regression Analysis will be applied to determine the combined and individual contributions of the socio-demographic and psychological variables (age, parenting style, body image, and locus of control) in predicting academic resilience among undergraduates.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the relationship among Parenting Styles, Locus of Control, Body Image and Academic Resilience among undergraduates in South-West Nigeria

Table 4.3 Correlation Matrix of Relationships among the variables

Correlation Matrix				
	Academic Resilience	Parenting Style	Locus of Control	Body Image
Academic Resilience	—			
Parenting Style	0.093	—		
Locus of Control	0.213***	-0.097	—	
Body Image	0.406***	-0.166*	0.365***	—

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

The correlation matrix reveals distinct patterns in the relationships among the four psychological variables among undergraduates in South West Nigeria. Academic Resilience shows a strong positive correlation with Body Image ($r = 0.406, p < .001$) and a moderate positive correlation with Locus of Control ($r = 0.213, p < .001$), indicating that students with more positive body image and a more internal locus of control tend to exhibit higher academic resilience. Notably, Academic Resilience has no significant relationship with Parenting Style ($r = 0.093, ns$). Body Image and Locus of Control are also strongly positively correlated ($r = 0.365, p < .001$), suggesting that students who feel more in control of their outcomes tend to have more positive

body perceptions. Parenting Style displays weak negative correlations with both Locus of Control ($r = -0.097$, ns) and Body Image ($r = -0.166$, $p < .05$), with only the latter reaching significance; this implies that more positive perceptions of parenting are slightly associated with less favorable body image, though the effect is small. Overall, the results suggest that Body Image and Locus of Control are the key factors positively linked to Academic Resilience in this sample, while Parenting Style plays a minimal or negligible role in these interrelationships.

Research Question Two: Research Question One: What is the Joint contribution of Parenting Styles, Locus of Control, Body Image to Academic Resilience among undergraduates in South-West Nigeria

Table 4.4 Showing joint contributions of independent variables to the dependent variable

Model Fit Measures						
			Overall Model Test			
Model	R	R ²	F	df1	df2	p
1	0.444	0.197	19.2	3	235	<.001

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=239

Omnibus ANOVA Test					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Parenting Style	87.4	1	87.4	7.98	0.005
Locus of Control	18.5	1	18.5	1.69	0.195
Body Image	444.0	1	444.0	40.54	<.001
Residuals	2573.7	235	11.0		

Note. Type 3 sum of squares

The multiple regression analysis examining the joint contribution of Parenting Style, Locus of Control, and Body Image to Academic Resilience among 239 undergraduates yielded a statistically significant model ($F(3, 235) = 19.2, p < .001$), with the three predictors collectively accounting for approximately 19.7% of the variance in Academic Resilience ($R = 0.444, R^2 = 0.197$). This indicates a moderate overall effect size, suggesting that these variables together explain a meaningful but not substantial portion of differences in students' academic resilience.

Research Question Three: What is the relative contribution of each of Parenting Styles, Locus of Control, Body Image to Academic Resilience among undergraduates in South-West Nigeria?

Table 4.5 relative contribution of each of Parenting Styles, Locus of Control, Body Image to Academic Resilience among undergraduates in South-West Nigeria

Model Coefficients - Academic Resilience

Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p	Stand. Estimate
Intercept	8.576	2.8909	2.97	0.003	
Parenting Style	0.191	0.0677	2.83	0.005	0.1676
Locus of Control	0.108	0.0829	1.30	0.195	0.0816
Body Image	0.418	0.0657	6.37	<.001	0.4038

The multiple regression model examining the relative contributions of the independent variables to Academic Resilience reveals clear differences in their individual predictive power after controlling for the others. Body Image emerged as the strongest predictor, with a significant positive standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.404, t = 6.37, p < .001$), indicating that a one standard deviation increase in Body Image is associated with a 0.404 standard deviation increase in Academic Resilience, accounting for the largest unique portion of variance. Parenting Style also contributed significantly ($\beta = 0.168, t = 2.83, p = 0.005$), showing a modest positive effect despite its non-significant bivariate correlation, suggesting it gains explanatory relevance in the multivariate context. In contrast, Locus of Control did not reach statistical significance ($\beta = 0.082, t = 1.30, p = 0.195$), implying that its initial moderate correlation with resilience is largely explained by shared variance with Body Image. Overall, while all predictors are positively related, Body Image dominates as the primary driver of academic resilience in this sample of Nigerian undergraduates, followed distantly by Parenting Style, with Locus of Control offering no substantial independent contribution.

Discussion of Findings

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This study investigated the predictors and demographic correlates of academic resilience among 239 undergraduates in South-West Nigeria. The research employed correlational and comparative designs to examine relationships between academic resilience, body image, locus of control, and parenting style, alongside differences by gender, marital status, university type, and level of study.

Key findings from the correlational analysis revealed strong positive associations between academic resilience and body image, as well as moderate links with locus of control, while parenting style showed negligible direct ties. Multiple regression analyses confirmed that body image emerged as the strongest independent predictor of academic resilience, uniquely explaining substantial variance even after controlling for shared effects. Parenting style contributed modestly but significantly in the multivariate context, suggesting contextual relevance despite weaker bivariate correlations. In contrast, locus of control's initial moderate association diminished to non-significance, indicating its influence was largely mediated or overlapped by body image.

Comparative analyses highlighted institutional and developmental influences on resilience. No significant gender differences were observed, with males and females reporting nearly identical means and medians, supported by negligible effect sizes. Similarly, marital status yielded no statistically significant differences, though a marginal trend toward higher resilience among the small married subsample approached conventional thresholds, potentially reflecting maturity benefits tempered by low power.

Significant variations emerged by university type, with private university students exhibiting the highest resilience levels, followed by federal and then state institutions. This pattern suggests institutional resources, stability, and selection effects in private settings foster greater adaptive capacity. Level of study also showed systematic differences, with resilience increasing progressively across years, peaking at 500 level and lowest among 100- and 200-level students. This trajectory points to cumulative experiential gains, maturity, and motivational factors in senior years.

Overall, the predictors collectively accounted for moderate variance in resilience, underscoring body image and locus of control as pivotal intrapersonal resources, with parenting exerting subtler influence during emerging adulthood. Demographic analyses portrayed resilience as equitable across gender and marital lines but sensitive to institutional and progressive developmental contexts. These insights align with resilience frameworks emphasizing protective personal and environmental factors in resource-constrained African higher education settings, where psychological assets buffer academic stressors.

Conclusion

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The findings of this study affirm that **academic resilience** among Nigerian undergraduates is shaped predominantly by intrapersonal factors, particularly positive body image, which stands out as a robust driver of perseverance amid challenges. This prominence underscores the protective role of self-acceptance in navigating societal pressures and academic demands, contributing to emotional fortitude essential for success in under-resourced environments. Demographically, the equivalence across gender supports equitable psychological resources, aligning with patterns in African contexts where shared stressors transcend traditional divides. The non-significant marital trend, though suggestive of maturity advantages, reinforces universal applicability of resilience-building efforts. Institutional disparities, favoring private universities, reveal structural inequities in public systems, where resource limitations and disruptions hinder adaptive development. The progressive increase by level of study confirms developmental maturation as a natural enhancer, with seniors benefiting from accrued coping strategies. In conclusion, these results position academic resilience as amenable to cultivation through targeted intrapersonal interventions, particularly those fostering body positivity and internal control, while addressing systemic gaps in public institutions. In Nigeria's higher education landscape—marked by overcrowding, funding shortages, and frequent disruptions—such resilience is vital for retention, performance, and well-being. By prioritizing individual agency over immutable demographics, the study advocates inclusive, evidence-based strategies to empower all students. Ultimately, enhancing resilience not only bolsters academic outcomes but contributes to broader psychological health, equipping graduates for societal contributions in a dynamic nation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. University Counselling and Wellness Programs: Institutions should integrate mandatory body image and self-acceptance workshops into orientation and ongoing support services, using evidence-based interventions like cognitive training apps to build resilience against appearance-related stressors.
2. Curriculum-Embedded Resilience Training: Develop modules on internal locus of control and adaptive coping, particularly for junior students (100–300 levels), to bridge developmental gaps and promote progressive resilience gains.
3. Institutional Equity Initiatives: Public (federal and state) universities should prioritize resource allocation, infrastructure upgrades, and strike mitigation policies to align resilience-supportive environments with private counterparts.
4. Gender-Neutral and Inclusive Approaches: Implement universal resilience programs without gender differentiation, while monitoring marital and socioeconomic subgroups for tailored maturity-based support.
5. Parenting and Family Engagement: Encourage transitional guidance for parents, emphasizing supportive styles that foster independence, through seminars or online resources.

6. Policy Advocacy: The National Universities Commission (NUC) and Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) should incentivize resilience research and programs, potentially extending targeted funding to public institutions for equity.

Suggestions for Further Studies

1. Employ longitudinal designs to track resilience trajectories across university years and clarify causal pathways.
2. Expand samples nationally, incorporating diverse regions and polytechnic/monotechnic students for broader applicability.
3. Investigate mediators/moderators like socioeconomic status or cultural factors in body image-resilience links.
4. Explore qualitative experiences of resilience in private versus public contexts to complement quantitative findings.
5. Examine intervention efficacy, such as body-positive programs, on resilience outcomes in controlled trials.

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